

Health and Spirituality: A transdisciplinary perspective on gender equality in India

Paulo Nuno Martins*
paulonunom@gmail.com

Abstract

By expatiating on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) of the 2030 Agenda of the United Nations, this essay makes a vivid connection between traditional beliefs, which portray the male child as overly important and superior to the female child and how such perspectives affect gender equality in India, especially since it threatens the very existence of the girl child. It also brings to light the theme that is fundamental for the sustainable development of the future generation of women in India, as defended by goal #5 of the SDG of the United Nations Agenda 2030, and linked it with goal #3 of the SDG of the United Nations Agenda 2030, that seeks to take care of all human beings in an integrated way (body, mind and soul), regardless of gender. This is described by the Transdisciplinary model of Reality and the "Hidden Third", and put into practice by the «Invisible Girl Project», the Foundation for Reproductive Health Services in India (FRHS) and the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare of the Government of India.

Keywords: Gender equality in India, Human Development Index (HDI), Goals #3 and #5 of the Sustainable Developments Goals of the 2030 Agenda of the United Nations, «Invisible Girl Project», Foundation for Reproductive Health Services in India (FRHS), the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare of the Government of India, Transdisciplinary model of Reality with the "Included Third" and the "Hidden Third".

Introduction

Several factors have contributed to selective abortions among Indian women in the last few decades. Most positively, several actions have also been taken, both by independent and governmental entities to minimize this situation and to contribute to the sustainable development of the Indian people, in particular, and humanity, in general. This essay intends to address this theme with particular emphasis on the interconnection between gender equality with tradition and health care, namely in India [1].

Photo 1: End Baby Girls Gendercide
Photo Source: Courtesy of *Invisible Girl P*

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The Human Development Index (HDI) [2], of the United Nations Program uses three evaluation criteria to measure the development of a country, namely: a) Longevity (the conditions of access to health care); b) Education Index (access to schooling); c) Income and cost of living (in each country).

* **Paulo Nuno Martins:** International Center for Transdisciplinary Research, CIRET, Paris, France; Transdisciplinary Center for Studies of Consciousness, CTEC, Fernando Pessoa University of Oporto, Portugal; Interuniversity Center of History of Science and Technology, CIUHCT, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Portugal.

One of the studies that the Human Development Index (HDI) has sought to verify is whether the Covid-19 pandemic

is a manifestation of the human species' imbalance with the planet Earth [3]. Thus, some investigations have been made to evaluate the effects of the Covid-19 pandemic on the worsening of life situation of people, in general, namely those with low income level, and therefore on their inability to access good health care (especially since immunization and vaccination rates are decreasing, in poor and developing countries and creating vulnerability in the human species) and quality education (the lack of access to the internet, in most developing countries, has hindered teaching in times of pandemic, and this has led to less schooling and consequently to a worse future development in the scientific and technological areas in these countries).

We will see some procedures on how to increase global awareness in the area of human relationships, so as to make room for equal opportunities for all human beings, regardless of race or gender and promote sustainable balance on planet Earth. The interconnection of health and gender equality, described by goal #3 (*“Ensuring a healthy life and promoting the well-being of all, at all ages”*) and goal #5 (*“Achieving gender equality and empowering all women and girls”*) of the Sustainable Development Goals of the 2030 Agenda of the United Nations, are also highlighted by this essay [4].

A case study that is related with this theme is the number of selective abortions that Indian women have been practicing in recent decades, either because they are under pressure from their families or their husbands, since in India there is still a preference for the birth of baby boys to baby girls.

Photo 2: Defend Children's Rights (Clothing, Food, Education).

Photo Source: Courtesy of *Invisible Girl Project*.

This fact is associated with the idea that the man can better support his parents and his wife financially, while the woman, usually with less education, finds herself in a situation where her parents have to pay “dowry” to a man to marry their daughter, especially since an unmarried lady or a divorced one is regarded as a disgrace to her family.

In this sense, the “Invisible Girl Project” [5] estimates that in the last 10 years, about 5 to 7 million female fetuses have been aborted, just due to gender reasons. For example, in 2011, the Indian census showed that for every 1000 boys there were 914 girls, with about 50 million girls and women missing in India, due to this selective abortion action in India. Furthermore, out of the Indian women who survive, 1 in every 4 does not get to reach adulthood, and out of those who do, about 27% marry before the age of 18 years old, and they become totally dependent on their husbands (financially, psychologically, etc).

Some concrete actions as a means of promoting gender equality are also taking place through «Invisible Girl Project» (IGP), with the “Rice Program”, which stands for rescue, intervention to respond quickly to emergencies on the field (e.g., food, clothes, etc), care of Indian girls, so female gendercide can no longer be ignored by people.

As defended by goal #3 of the SDG of the United Nations Agenda 2030, the integrative medicine model in health care seeks to see every human being in its various dimensions (body, mind and soul), regardless of gender (male or female), as referred to by the World Health Organization (WHO) [6] which defines that *“health is a complete state of physical, mental and social well-being and not just the absence of disease or infirmity”*. This perspective reinforces the importance of gender equality for

the sustainable development of humanity, as defended by goal #5 of the SDG of the United Nations Agenda 2030.

However, there are some studies performed by the Foundation for Reproductive Health Services in India (FRHS) that show the effect of the Covid-19 pandemic on the worsening life situation of Indian women [7]. In fact, part of India's health systems have been converted into treatment centers to combat Covid-19 pandemic which have contributed to the increase of more than 2 million unplanned pregnancies, and more than 800 000 abortions without the desired medical care.

In this regard, the Government of India [8], particularly the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare has been taking some measures to minimize selective abortion, namely by limiting the sale of portable ultrasound devices, laboratory tests that reveal the sex of the fetus (prenatal examination), especially in urban areas. It also created the "Pregnancy Program 2020" which extends the time to perform abortions up to 24 weeks, in the cases of rape, fetal deficiency and unwanted pregnancy in teenagers in order to promote the dignity, autonomy and security of Indian women.

Furthermore, in 2000, only 25,2% of births in India took place in Government hospitals. In 2005, the total value was 34.5%, and in 2014, 52% of births in India took place in Government hospitals and 26.5% occurred in private hospitals, for a total of 78.5%.

Alongside these actions, it has been implementing several programs to reduce illiteracy rates, which mainly affect Indian women, by promoting compulsory education to the entire Indian population, regardless of gender. For example, in 2001, according to gender (>7 years), the difference between the literacy rate was 21.6%. In 2011, according to gender (>7 years), the female literacy rate (64.7%) was still lower than the male literacy rate (80.9%), but with only a 16.3% difference between genders. These actions aim to change rooted patterns of behavior of several generations which are associated with cultural and caste issues, and have severely penalized the lives of Indian women.

Probably, only the next generations of Indian women will take advantage of the actions currently implemented, in terms of health and education, and which will be reflected in the improvement of the conditions of their lives, as it already exists for a large percentage of European, North American and Canadian women.

However, until Modernity, Subject and Object were totally separated, and the notion of dominance and power of the Subject over the Object were exalted. The Cartesian paradigm is included in this model of reality.

Photo 3: Provide Family Counseling. **Photo Source:** Courtesy of *Invisible Girl Project*.

Photo 4: Rescue Teenagers from Forced Marriage. **Photo Source:** Courtesy of *Invisible Girl Project*.

Photo 5: Provide Medical Care for all Girls and Women. **Photo Source:** Courtesy of *Invisible Girl Project*.

In this model, the separation of the mind (exclusive domain of philosophy and religion) and the body (exclusive domain of science and medicine) is defended, with the body being treated as a “machine”. This “paradigm of simplification” separated the thinking Subject from the known Object, that is, philosophy and science. Then, it reduced the “complex to simple” through a hyper-specialization that isolates objects from their environment. This process is called “blind intelligence” by Edgar Morin. In this sense, António Damásio argues that “Descartes’ Error” is to consider that the mind can exist separate and independent from the body, as feelings and emotions are an important link between reason and body, being indispensable in the survival of mankind. Furthermore, Edward Wilson in his book “Génesis” defends the intersection of spirituality and science, as he shows that species that demonstrate the strength of cooperation and the power of altruism present greater complexity and possibility of survival.

In this regard, Basarab Nicolescu [9] has proposed a new paradigm characteristic of Cosmodernity where the contradictories (A and non-A) are unified by the “Included Third”. There is a zone of non-resistance between the levels of Reality that corresponds to the Sacred and where the “Hidden Third” unifies the Subject and Object (the supreme contradictories) that is not “rationalizable”, as defended by Edgar Morin.

In Eastern thought, the Indian philosophies defend the existence of several levels of perception and Reality, described by the Theory of Pancha Koshas [10]. These several plans of consciousness in human beings are: Annamaya kosha (physical body), Pranamaya kosha (vital or pranic body), Kamamaya kosha (feelings and desire), Manasmaya kosha (concrete or rational mind), Vijñanamaya kosha (abstract mind), Anandamaya kosha (intuitive mind or conscious linkage with soul), and Monad (spirit).

Photo 6: Support Middle Education for all Girls.

Photo Source: Courtesy of *Invisible Girl Project*.

In Western thought, the ontological axiom of Transdisciplinarity is founded in the existence of different levels of Reality of the Subject and, correspondingly, different levels of Reality of the Object. The several levels of consciousness described by the Theory of Panchakoshas might be related with the several levels of Reality and complexity proposed by Basarab Nicolescu.

The introduction of levels of Reality introduces a multidimensional structure of Reality. Every level of Reality is characterized by its incompleteness, that is, knowledge is forever open and is simultaneously exterior and interior.

The different levels of Reality of the Object are accessible to our knowledge due to the different levels of perception that are potentially present in our being (body, mind, soul). If inner perception of the Subject expands then the levels of Reality of the Object increases too. This is the deepest reason why gender equality is fundamental for the balanced development of humanity.

Thus, in Cartesian Binary Partition (Subject versus Object), characteristic of Classical and Modernity, there is only one level of Reality; In Transdisciplinary Ternary Partition (Subject, Object, Hidden Third), characteristic of Cosmodernity, we simultaneously consider the asymmetries of the levels of Reality and the symmetry of the Hidden Third, situated in a *non-time*. The levels of Reality are generated by the breaking of symmetry due to *time*. This is the transdisciplinary model of Reality or Trans-Reality (ternary structure of Reality), whose perspective allows the harmonious integration between science, culture, society and spirituality. The sustainable future necessary for our human survival depends on our current choices, as active participants in the Universe, where our true being is reflected through the other human being, regardless of gender, race, belief, etc.

Conclusions

Edgar Morin [11], in an introduction to complex thinking, talked about some investigations conducted by scientists Humberto Maturana and Francisco Varela, in which he said that biological systems show that they are self-poetic and self-conscious, such self-awareness/self-perception influences the factor that determines the structure of the entire “network” organization and therefore its own complexity.

Another aim of this essay is to highlight the interdependence between biological systems, as it affects the interconnection of gender equality and the sustainability of the planet Earth. The urgency to respect a fundamental human right, referred to by the goal #5 of the Sustainable Developments Goals of the United Nations Agenda 2030, as a “*necessary principle for peace, prosperity and world sustainability*”. This perspective is linked with the goal #3 of the SDG of the United Nations Agenda 2030, that seeks to take care of all human beings in an integrated way (body, mind and soul), regardless of gender, that is, a balance between our male side (our conscious side) and our female side (our unconscious side) [12]. **T**

Photo 7: Encourage Higher Education to Empower Woman. **Photo Source:** Courtesy of *Invisible Girl Project*.

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